

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RP-HPLC ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
ENALAPRIL MALEATE AND HYDROCHLOROTHIAZIDE IN
TABLET****Ms. Aditi Arun Mhatre¹, Ms. Kajal Ramraj Yadav²**^{1,2} Lecturer, AIMS College Of Pharmacy, Aims foundation, Vadvali Dombivali (E)-421204**Abstract:**

The present study outlines the development and validation of a simple, precise, accurate, and robust Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous estimation of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide in tablet dosage form. The chromatographic separation was achieved using a Kromasil C18 column (250mm × 2.1mm, 1.5 μm) with a mobile phase consisting of Methanol: Acetonitrile: Ammonium Acetate Buffer (pH 4.5) in the ratio of 40:30:30 v/v, at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detection wavelength of 230 nm. The retention times of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide were found to be 3.841 and 5.652 minutes, respectively. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for parameters including linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, robustness, ruggedness, LOD, and LOQ. Linearity was observed in the range of 5–30 μg/mL for both drugs with correlation coefficients greater than 0.999. Recovery studies indicated accuracy within the acceptable limits. The method demonstrated suitable system suitability parameters with acceptable resolution, tailing factor, and theoretical plate count. The proposed RP-HPLC method is suitable for routine quality control of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: Enalapril Maleate, Hydrochlorothiazide, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Method Validation, Simultaneous Estimation, ICH Guidelines, Linearity, Accuracy, Precision, Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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Please cite this article in press Aditi Arun Mhatre et al., *Rp-Hplc Analytical Method Development And Validation For Simultaneous Estimation Of Enalapril Maleate And Hydrochlorothiazide In Tablet*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(06).

INTRODUCTION:**Method development of drugs:**

The analyte is enough to know the information of the compound. One can select the most suitable HPLC method development by the physical and chemical characteristics and by a vast literature review. Information regarding the sample can be achieved by molecular weight, structure, functionality, Pka value, UV-spectra and solubility of the compound. By knowing whether the pure compound is organic soluble or water soluble, one can select the best mobile phase and column for HPLC method development. In many laboratories, typical detectors like Mass spectroscopy, UV-Visible detectors are used as they can detect a wide variety of compounds. Analytical methods are intended to establish the identity, purity, physical characteristics and potency of the drugs. To support drug testing against specifications that arise during manufacturing and quality release operators, as well as during long-term stability studies and for safety and characterization studies or evolution of drug performance, methods are developed.

Before the final method optimization, all individual components should be investigated during the preliminary method development. By this, it is easy to evaluate the method performance in each component and streamline the final method optimization. Resolving power, specificity and speed are the major attributes of method development. By combining different factors like composition of solvent, type of stationary phase, mobile phase, P" and buffers, selectivity can be achieved.

For the chromatographic separation, changing solvents and stationary phases, proper range of P are the most suitable approaches. Better chromatographic resolution can be achieved by the P" ranging from 1-12 and the development of the method depends upon column efficiency, selectivity and retention time. For chromatographic separation, mobile phase composition or strength plays a vital role.

The most commonly used solvents in RP-HPLC are acetonitrile, methyl alcohol and Tetra hydro furan (having the wavelength of 190, 205 & 212nm).

By the selection of right column temperature and changing the mobile phase, the separation of many samples can be enhanced.

Method validation of drugs:

According to ISO definition, validation is defined as "Verification, where the specified requirements are adequate for an intended use." Method validation can

be used for qualitative, semi-quantitative or quantitative methods.

The scientific soundness of the measurement or characterization and also to varying extents throughout the regulatory submission process, the validation of analytical method is required. The method development includes the measurement of the correct substance, in correct amount and in appropriate range. The goal of method validation is to identify the critical parameters and to establish the acceptance criteria of system suitability.

The effort done in method development and optimisation leads to the effective development of HPLC method and its final performance. For the method development of samples in chromatographic separation, method validation is very important.

INTRODUCTION TO QUALITY BY DESIGN:

Quality has been given an importance by all regulatory bodies for pharmaceutical products. Quality means customer satisfaction in terms of service, product, and process. Many of these quality related activities reflect need for companies to excel in global competition. Customer demands the perfection in quality, reliability, low cost and timely performance. Customer satisfaction can be achieved by two ways i.e. features and free from deficiencies in goods. The features like performance, trustworthiness, robustness, ease of use, and serviceability have to be built in the product and such product should be free from deficiencies. Quality, productivity, cost, cycle time and value are interrelated terms. Quality activities must try to detect quality problems early enough to permit actions without requiring compromise in cost, schedule or quality. The emphasis must be on precaution rather than on just correction of quality problems. Quality can be the driving force to empower results in other parameters. Hence the quality has to be built in the product as well as services through proper planning, so that the forthcoming failure can be avoided. Mere analysis of final product will not work but the quality should be designed in the product. The concept of quality by design was summarized by a well-known quality expert Joseph Moses Juran; he believed that quality could be planned and that most quality associated problems have their origin in the way which quality was planned in the first place.

Regulatory aspects to QbD**1. FDA perspective**

In 2005 USFDA asked participating firms to submit chemistry manufacturing control (CMC) information demonstrating application of QbD as part of New

Drug Application. QbD involves thorough understanding of process; a goal or objective is defined before actual start of process. Design space and real time release risk assessment are other parameters for implementation of QbD. International conference on harmonization in its Q8 pharmaceutical development, Q9 quality risk assessment and Q10 pharmaceutical quality system gives stringent requirements regarding quality of product. FDA also states the importance of quality of pharmaceutical products by giving Process Analytical Technology (PAT) which is a Framework for Innovative Pharmaceutical Development, Manufacturing and Quality Assurance.

2. ICH guideline and QbD (ICH guideline Q8, 2012; ICH guideline Q10, 2012; ICH guideline Q9, 2012)

The underlying principles of QbD i.e. science and risk-based product development, risk assessment, lifecycle approach and method design are explained in the quality guidelines of international conference on harmonization i.e. ICH Q8 Pharmaceutical Development, ICHQ9 Quality Risk Management, and ICH Q10 Pharmaceutical Quality System.

3. Regulatory challenges and inspection

According to Anastasia G. Lolas and Anurag S. Rathore "In a QbD concept, the regulatory burden is less because there are wider ranges and limits based on product and process understanding. Changes within these ranges and limits do not require prior approval".

Traditionally, inspections have been conducted using the FDA system-based approach and in accordance with CDER's Compliance Program "Inspection of Licensed Biological Therapeutic Drug Products". But now query arises that how the inspection will take place in the present scenario where QbD is mandated. During prelicense or preapproval inspections under a QbD concept, the FDA inspection team will assess the implementation and effectiveness of the process design as described in the application and whether knowledge and risk management have been transferred successfully from development to manufacturing. The inspection will evaluate the quality system and its effectiveness regarding consistent product quality, change in control procedures, process improvements, deviation management, and knowledge and risk management during the product lifecycle. Inspection of facility and equipment qualification and maintenance as well as raw material screening and supplier management will be same as it was performed previously. But design, testing, and monitoring programmes that demonstrate robustness and consistency would be highlighted.

4. Basic considerations of QbD

As far as pharmaceutical industry is considered safety of patient and providing a quality product have been given prime importance; and to achieve this target QbD assist it by thorough understanding of process which is the ultimate goal of QbD.

Advantages of QbD can be summarized as,

- Patient safety and product efficacy are focused.
- Scientific understanding of pharmaceutical process and methods is done.
- It involves product design and process development. Science based risk assessment is carried.
- Critical quality attributes are identified and their effect on final quality of product is analysed.
- It offers robust method or process.
- Business benefits are also driving force to adopt QbD.
- Method design concept helps to avoid cost involved with post approval changes.

4.1 Elements of pharmaceutical development

QbD comprises all elements of pharmaceutical development mentioned in the ICH guideline Q8. Pharmaceutical Development section is projected to provide a complete understanding of the product and manufacturing process for reviewers and inspectors.

- Different elements of pharmaceutical development include,
- Defining an objective
- Determination of critical quality attributes (CQA)
- Risk assessment

4.1.1. Define an objective

Quality target profile (QTP) forms the basis of QbD, which is in relation to the predefined objective criteria mentioned in the definition of QbD.

As per ICH guideline Q8 R2 the Quality Target Product Profile forms the basis for design and the development of the product. Considerations for the Quality Target Product Profile could include:

- Intended use in clinical setting,
- route of administration,
- dosage form, delivery Systems.
- Dosage strength(s),

Drug product quality criteria like sterility, purity, stability and drug release as appropriate for dosage form the intended for marketing.

QbD requires a Target Product Profile; it may be called as Quality Target Product Profile (QTPP) which defines the expectations in final product. In case of analytical method development, it is called as analytical target profile (ATP), it is also called as Target Product Profile (TPP).

4.1.2. Determination of critical quality attributes. (CQA)

According to ICH Q8 R2 "A CQA is a physical, chemical, biological, or microbiological property or characteristic that should be within an appropriate limit, range, or distribution to ensure the desired product quality". CQAs are generally linked with the drug substance, excipients, intermediates (in process materials) and drug product. For example, CQAs of solid oral dosage forms are typically those aspects affecting product purity, strength, drug release and stability whereas for parenteral they are Sterility and clarity. The CQAs can additionally include properties like particle size distribution, bulk density that affect drug product. Mostly CQAs are derived from the Quality Target Product Profile and/or prior knowledge is used to guide the product and process development and Subsequently CQAs are accessed for risk management.

Dissolution test is crucial for a controlled release drug product and on other hand dissolution test for an immediate release drug product which belongs to the high aqueous solubility and high permeability i.e. BCS class I drug will not prove as critical attribute for quality control viewpoint. CQA differs for type process, dosage form, and type of method development hence thorough knowledge of real time data to working scientists is important.

4.1.3. Risk assessment

It is commonly understood that risk is defined as the combination of the probability of occurrence of harm and the severity of that harm. Risk assessment helps to increase quality of method or process. Also, it is determinant for effect of input variable on method or processes. From risk assessment one can recognize critical attributes that are going to affect final quality of product. A risk assessment is helpful for effective communication between FDA and industry, research/development and manufacturing and among multiple manufacturing sites within company. There may be risk and uncertainty in validation of bioanalytical method though the guidelines for validation are given by various regulatory bodies there may be a variation in interpretation of those guidelines and hence in experimental method designing which leads to unfit method development for intended purpose. Risk management for excipients to determine shelf life can be done by statistical parameters.

Principles of quality risk management are:

- Scientific knowledge-based evaluation of the risk to quality which eventually links to the protection of the patient.
- Adequate effort should be taken; formality and documentation of the quality risk

management process should be done with the level of risk involved.

- Risk management is joint responsibility of quality unit, business development, engineering, regulatory affairs, production operations, sales and marketing, legal, statistics and clinical department.
- Methods of risk assessment: Some methods of risk assessment are mentioned in ICH guideline Q9 as follows:

ICH guideline Q9 gives description of risk management and various terminologies associated with it, like Risk Acceptance, Risk Analysis, Risk Assessment, Risk Communication, Risk Control, Risk Evaluation, Risk Identification, and Risk Management. Quality management policies should mention procedures and practices to the tasks of assessing, controlling, communicating and reviewing risk. Risk Reduction is actions taken to lessen the probability of occurrence of harm and the severity of that harm.

4.1.4. Development of experimental design

Experimental design is the multidimensional combination and interaction of input variables (e.g., material attributes) and process parameters that have been demonstrated to provide assurance of quality. Design space is proposed by the applicant and is subject to regulatory assessment and approval of ICH Q8 (R2). Pharmaceutical development scientists have begun making use of computer aided process design (CAPD) and process simulation to support process development and optimization of manufacturing. Risk assessment can guide to understand linkage and effect of process parameters and material attributes on product, and ranges for variables within which consistent quality can be achieved. These parameters or attributes are selected for addition in the design space. Information regarding reason for inclusion of some variables in design space as well as exclusion of other variable has to be mentioned.

4.1.5. Designing and implementing control strategy

Control strategy is required to ensure that material and process are within the expected lower and upper limits. Parameter and material are routinely controlled during production in order to assure reproducibility. The control space should be within the design space. Generally, scale up is trial and error basis. During scale, up processes parameters may differ but attributes which affect quality remain the same hence control strategy is required. QbD gives trace on reproducibility and robustness. Process capability index expresses reproducibility of process.

Method Validation

This process consists of establishments of the performance characteristics and the limitation of the method.

Method Performance Parameters are Determined using Equipment that is:

Within specification

Working correctly

Adequately calibrated

Method Validation is required when:

A new method is being developed

Revision of the established method

When established method are used in different laboratories and by different analysts etc.

Comparison of method

When quality control indicates method changes

Drug Profile

Performance characteristics examined when carrying out method validation are:

- Accuracy
- Precision
- Specificity
- Selectivity
- Sensitivity
- Limit of detection.
- Limit of quantification
- Linearity and Range
- Ruggedness
- Robustness
- System suitability

1. Hydrochlorothiazide	
Name	Hydrochlorothiazide
Hydrochlorothiazide	A thiazide diuretic always considered the prototypical member of this class. It reduces the reabsorption of electrolytes from the renal tubules
Structure	<p>Fig No.2.1 Structure of Hydrochlorothiazide</p>
CAS NO	58-93-5
Molecular Formula	C ₇ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₄ S ₂
Molecular Weight	297.739 g/mol
Monoisotopic Mass	296.964 g/mol
IUPAC Name	6-chloro-1,1-dioxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-126,2,4-benzothiadiazine-7-sulfonamide
Category	This medication is used to treat high blood pressure.
Colour	White Powder
pKa	9.09 (strongest acidic) -2.7 (Strongest Basic)
Melting point	266-268°C
Water Solubility	Aqueous solubility: 722 mg/L (at 25 °C)
Storage	Store at room temperature away from light and moisture.
Uses	Hydrochlorothiazide is a thiazide diuretic (water pill) that helps prevent your body from absorbing too much salt, which can cause fluid retention Hydrochlorothiazide is used to treat high blood pressure (hypertension) Hydrochlorothiazide is also used to treat fluid retention (edema) in people with congestive heart failure, cirrhosis of the liver, or kidney disorders, or edema caused by taking steroids or estrogen

2. Enalapril Maleate	
Name	Enalapril Maleate
Description	Enalapril is an ACE inhibitor. ACE stands for angiotensin converting enzyme.
Structure	<p>Fig No.2.2 Structure of Enalapril Maleate</p>
CAS NO	76095-16-4
Molecular Formula	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₅
Molecular Weight	492.525 g/mol
Monoisotopic Mass	492.210 g/mol
IUPAC Name	(2S)-1-[(2S)-2-([(2S)-1-ethoxy-1-oxo-4-phenylbutan-2-yl)amino]propanoyl]pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid; (2Z)-but-2-enedioic acid
Category	Enalapril is an ACE inhibitor. ACE stands for angiotensin converting enzyme. Enalapril is used to treat high blood pressure (hypertension)
Colour	White Powder
pka	3.67 (strongest acidic) 5.2 (Strongest Basic)
Melting point	160-162 °C
Water Solubility	Aqueous solubility: 0.213 mg/mL
Storage	Store at room temperature away from light and moisture.
Uses	Enalapril is a prodrug belonging to the angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor drug class that works on the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, which is responsible for the regulation of blood pressure and fluid and electrolyte homeostasis. Enalapril is an orally-active and long-acting nonsulphydryl antihypertensive agent that suppresses the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system to lower blood pressure.

Materials and Methods

Material:

Table No.1.1 Active Pharmaceutical Drug

Sr. No.	Name	Description
1.	Enalapril Maleate	White powder, Amorphous. To treat high blood pressure (hypertension).
2.	Hydrochlorothiazide	Yellowish powder, To help reduce the amount of water in the body by increasing the flow of urine.
3.	Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide USP	5 mg Enalapril Maleate and 12.5 mg Hydrochlorothiazide contain each tablet. Drug Manufactured and Marketed by Intas Pharmaceuticals Ltd

Table No.1.2 List of Chemicals use in Research work

Sr No.	Name of Chemical	Molecular Formula	Properties	Manufacturer
1.	Acetonitrile	C ₂ H ₃ N	Solvent, BP 76-81.6°C	Merck Life science
2.	Methanol	CH ₃ OH	Flammable Solvent	Merck Life science
3.	Ammonium Acetate Buffer	NH ₄ CH ₃ CO ₂	White Crystalline Powder	SD Fine Chem. Ltd, Mumbai
4.	Distilled Water	H ₂ O	Universal Solvent, BP 100°C	Inhouse

Sr. No.	Name of Equipment's/Instruments	Model/Specification	Manufacturer
1	HPLC	Series 3000	Schimadzu Ultimate3000
	Pump	PU2080	
	Sample Injection	Autosampler	
	UV/Vis Detector	UV 2075 plus	
	Software	Chromolin	
2	pH Meter	101	Chemiline
3	Balance	AY-120	Shimadzu
4	Sonicator	UCB-40	Rolex
5	Deep Freezer	-	Blue Star
6	Refrigerator	-	Godrej

Table No.1.3 List of Instruments

1.1.2 Methods

Preliminary Analysis of Drug

a) Description

Color and texture of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide were compared with reported characters mentioned in drug bank

b) Solubility

Solubility of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was determined in various organic solvents like water, methanol, ethanol and Acetonitrile.

c) UV Analysis

UV analysis was carried out by scanning the solution of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide at 200-400 nm. And lambda max was found to be 230nm.

3. Preparation of Buffer: Take 1000mL of Water and add 2.54 gm of Ammonium Acetate Buffer. Mixed well and set pH 4.5 with dilute Orthophosphoric acid. Then prepare filter and degassed for 10 minutes.

Mobile Phase: Mixed above buffer and added Methanol + Acetonitrile in the ratio of 30:70 v/v.

4. Preparation of stock solutions of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide

Stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10 mg Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide in Methanol and then diluted with Methanol in 10 ml of volumetric flask to get concentration of 1000 µg/ml. From the resulting solution 0.1 ml was diluted to 10 ml with water to obtain concentration of 10 µg/ml of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide and labelled as standard stock Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide.

5. Selection of detection wavelength

From the standard stock solution further dilutions were done using water and scanned over the range of 200-400 nm and the spectra were overlain. It was observed that drug showed considerable absorbance at 230 nm.

Trail 1

Fig no 1.1: Chromatogram of Trail 1

Mobile phase	Methanol: Water (50:50)
Selection of column	Kromasil C18 (250mm x 2.1mm ID, Particle size: 1.5 μ m)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Retention Time	Enalapril Maleate-2.615 minutes Hydrochlorothiazide - No Peak Observed
Run time	14.00 minutes
Resolution	-
Column temperature	Room Temperature (30°C)
Detection wavelength	230nm
Conclusion	Only enalapril was detected. RT of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was not good as expected, Theoretical Plate was not more than 2000, Resolution was good, peak splitting observed. No optimised condition, hence peak was rejected.

Trail 2

Fig no 1.2: Chromatogram of Trail 2

Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: Water (50:50)
Selection of column	Kromasil C18 (250mm x 2.1mm ID, Particle size: 1.5 μ m)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Retention Time	Enalapril Maleate - No Peak Observed Hydrochlorothiazide - 2.615 minutes
Run time	14.00 minutes
Resolution	-
Column temperature	Room Temperature (30°C)
Detection wavelength	230nm
Conclusion	Only Hydrochlorothiazide was detected. RT of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was not good as expected, Theoretical Plate was not more than 2000, Resolution was good, peak splitting observed and base line was not corrected. No optimised condition, hence peak was rejected

Trail 3

Fig No 1.3: Chromatogram of Trail 3

Mobile phase	Methanol: ACN: Ammonium Acetate Buffer pH 5.5 (25:25:50)
Selection of column	Kromasil C18 (250mm x 2.1mm ID, Particle size: 1.5 μ m)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Retention Time	Enalapril Maleate - 8.204 minutes Hydrochlorothiazide 8.995 minutes
Run time	12.00 minutes
Resolution	1.03
Column temperature	Room Temperature
Detection wavelength	230nm
Conclusion	RT of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was not good as expected, Theoretical Plate was not more than 2000, Resolution was not more than 2.0, no tailing observed. No optimised condition, hence peak was rejected.

Trail 4

Fig no 1.4: Chromatogram of Trail 4

Mobile phase	Methanol: ACN: Ammonium Acetate Buffer pH 4.0 (30:30:40)
Selection of column	Kromasil C18 (250mm x 2.1mm ID, Particle size: 1.5 μ m)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Retention Time	Enalapril Maleate-4.581 minutes Hydrochlorothiazide 6.658 minutes
Run time	9.00 minutes
Resolution	2.01
Column temperature	Room Temperature
Detection wavelength	230nm
Conclusion	RT of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was not good as expected, Theoretical Plate was not more than 2000, Resolution was not more than 2.0, tailing observed. No optimised condition, hence peak was rejected.

Trail 5

Fig no 1.5: Chromatogram of Trail 5

Mobile phase	Methanol: ACN: Ammonium Acetate Buffer pH 4.0 (30:30:40)
Selection of column	Kromasil C18 (250mm x 2.1mm ID, Particle size: 1.5 μ m)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Retention Time	Enalapril Maleate 4.541 minutes Hydrochlorothiazide 5.597 minutes
Run time	9.00 minutes
Resolution	1.78
Column temperature	Room Temperature
Detection wavelength	230nm
Conclusion	RT of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was good as expected, Theoretical Plate was more than 2000, Resolution was not more than 2.0, no tailing observed. No optimised condition, hence peak was rejected.

Trial-6 (Optimized Trial)

Fig no 1.6: Chromatogram of Trail 6

Mobile phase	Methanol: ACN: Ammonium Acetate Buffer pH 4.5 (40:30:30)
Selection of column	Kromasil C18 (250mm x 2.1mm ID, Particle size: 1.5 μ m)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Retention Time	Enalapril Maleate 3.841 minutes Hydrochlorothiazide 5.652 minutes
Run time	9.00 minutes
Resolution	2.86
Column temperature	Room Temperature
Detection wavelength	230nm
Conclusion	RT of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was good as expected, Theoretical Plate was more than 2000, Resolution was great, no tailing observed. all pear properties passes, Optimized Chromatographic condition.

METHOD VALIDATION

Mobile phase consisting of Ammonium Acetate buffer: Methanol: Acetonitrile (30:40:30 v/v/v) pH adjusted to 4.5 with orthophosphoric acid. at 230 nm with a flow rate 1.0 ml/min was used for the present method. The method was validated for the parameters such as system suitability, linearity and range, precision, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness limit of quantitation (LOQ) and limit of detection (LOD) as per ICH guidelines.

1. Linearity:

The peak area response for Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was found to be linearity from 5% to 30% level of working concentration of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide respectively. Linearity graphs of concentration (as x-value) versus area (as y-value) were plotted (Figure 7.1) and correlation coefficient, y-intercept and slope of the regression were calculated (Table 7.1). The Correlation coefficient (R) were found to be >0.99.

Table 1.4: Linearity of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide

Sr.No.	Injection	Peak Area		
		Concentration (µg/ml)	Enalapril Maleate	Hydrochlorothiazide
1.	1.	6	501483	824695
2.	2.	12	1002966	1649390
3.	3.	18	1454449	2424085
4.	4.	24	2005932	3298780
5.	5.	30	2507415	4123475
6.	6.	36	3008898	4948170

Fig No. 1.8: Calibration Curve of Enalapril Maleate

Fig No. 1.9: Calibration Curve of Hydrochlorothiazide

Fig No. 1.10: Chromatogram for injection 1

Fig No.2.1: Chromatogram for injection 2

Fig No.2.2: Chromatogram for injection 3

Fig No.2.3: Chromatogram for injection 4

Fig No.2.4: Chromatogram for injection 5

Fig No.2.5: Chromatogram for injection 6

Table No.1.5 Characteristic parameters of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide for the proposed HPLC method.

Parameter	Result	
	Enalapril Maleate	Hydrochlorothiazide
Calibration range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	
Detection wavelength (nm)	230 nm	
Regression equation (y^*)	$Y=83819x+1333$	$Y=137687x+13333$
Slope (b)	83819	137687
Intercept (a)	1333	13333
Correlation coefficient(12)	0.9995	0.9998

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the method was determined by performing recovery studies. The known amount of standard Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide at 80%, 100%, and 120% levels to the preanalyzed sample was added followed by replicate quantitative analysis using proposed Diluent. The samples were dissolved in methanol filtered using membrane filter 0.22 μ . The percentage recoveries were calculated against respective levels.

Table no 1.6: Recovery study for Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide

Recovery level	Enalapril Maleate		Hydrochlorothiazide	
	% Recovery	Average % Recovery	% Recovery	Average % Recovery
80%-1	99.35	98.65	99.18	99.14
80%-2	97.89		98.82	
80%-3	99.96		99.54	
100%-1	99.82	99.81	100.22	100.14
100%-2	99.52		99.02	
100%-3	99.98		101.21	
120%-1	100.71	100.09	100.26	99.49
120%-2	99.34		99.74	
120%-3	100.12		99.20	

System Precision and Method Precision:

System precision was evaluated by injecting six replicate of standard solutions containing 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Enalapril Maleate and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Hydrochlorothiazide using chromatographic conditions mentioned earlier. The average peak areas were determined and the results were expressed in terms of percent relative standard deviation (% RSD). For method precision the six replicates of sample solutions (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Enalapril Maleate and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Hydrochlorothiazide) were analyzed as per proposed method. The % assay of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was calculated and results were expressed in terms of % RSD.

Intermediate Precision

Intra Day and inter day precision studies were carried out to determine the Intermediate precision at three different concentration level at regular interval of time in a day and on three different days in triplicate. The % assay of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was calculated and the results were expressed in terms of %RSD.

Table 1.7: Precision Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide

Precision			
Repeatability			
Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Peak Area Enalapril Maleate	Peak Area Hydrochlorothiazide
1.	24	2011150	3303998
2.	24	1991150	3283998
3.	24	2011163	3304011
4.	24	2004276	3297124
5.	24	2061150	3353998
6.	24	2008938	3301786
Average		2014637.8	3307485.8
Standard Deviation		21905.7	21905.7
RSD%		1.087	0.662

System Suitability:

The mixed standard solution each was injected into the HPLC system. The system suitability parameters such as resolution, capacity factor, theoretical plates/meter, Retention times and peak symmetry were recorded.

Table no 1.8: System suitability

Parameters	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	%RSD of Peak areas	Retention Time
Enalapril Maleate	1.01	7626	1.04	3.841
Hydrochlorothiazide	1.13	12188	0.95	5.692
Acceptance Criteria	NMT 2.0	NLT 2000	NMT 2.0	-

Specificity:

The specificity of the method was demonstrated by injecting mobile phase, standard (STD) solutions (10 µg/ml of Enalapril Maleate and 10 µg/ml of Hydrochlorothiazide) and sample solutions (10 µg/ml of Enalapril Maleate and 10 µg/ml of Hydrochlorothiazide) in HPLC system each in triplicates. The chromatograms of mobile phase, standard and sample solutions were obtained and studied for any interference at the retention time of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide.

The specificity of method was determined by comparing the chromatograms of the blank, standard (STD) solutions and sample solutions, which revealed that no peaks were co-eluted with Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide peak from blank (Figure 7.11, 7.12 and 7.13). Also no purity flag was observed for Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide from sample solution and standard solution. Hence, the method was found to be specific

Fig no 2.6: Chromatogram of STD Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide solution

Figure no 2.7: Chromatogram of sample solution

Robustness:

The robustness of the developed method was determined by changing the pH from 3.4 to 3:6 and flow rate from 0.9 ml/min to 1.1 ml/min. The retention times and other system suitability parameters were determined and % RSD for each parameter was recorded and compared with the limits as per ICH guidelines.

Table no 1.9 : Robustness Enalapril Maleate

Robustness					
Sr. No	Parameter		Response	Parameter	Response
Acetonitrile: Potassium Phosphate Buffer			Retention Time (min)	Detection Wavelength	Peak Area
(V/V)				(nm)	
1.	69	31	3.823	228	1997805
2.	70	30	3.849	230	2006120
3.	71	29	3.909	232	2029384
Average			3.841	Average	1997770
Standard Deviation			0.080	Standard Deviation	37850.36
RSD%			1.083	RSD%	1.495

Table no 1.10 : Robustness Hydrochlorothiazide

Robustness					
Sr. No	Parameter		Response	Parameter	Response
Acetonitrile: Potassium Phosphate Buffer			Retention Time (min)	Detection Wavelength	Peak Area
(V/V)				(nm)	
1.	69	31	5.562	228	3240653
2.	70	30	5.659	230	3298968
3.	71	29	5.758	232	3332232
Average			5.660	Average	3290618
Standard Deviation			0.080	Standard Deviation	37850.36
RSD%			1.414	RSD%	1.150

Ruggedness

The ruggedness of method was determined by injecting the six replicates of preanalyzed sample as per the proposed method by different analyst. The results were represented as % RSD exceeding not more than 2.0%

Table no 2.1 : Ruggedness

Sample No.	% Assay of Enalapril Maleate	% Assay of Hydrochlorothiazide
1.	98.81	98.25
2.	99.02	97.88
3.	100.02	99.28
4.	99.32	99.89
5.	99.72	97.92
6.	99.08	98.48
Mean	99.17	98.89
% RSD	0.89	0.79

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ):

LOD is the lowest concentration of the analyte which can be detected. LOQ is the smallest concentration of the analyte which can be detected as well as quantified accurately. The LOD and LOQ were calculated using the following formula (equation 1 and 2),

$$\text{LOD} = 3.30 \sigma$$

$$S \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 1}$$

Where, σ - standard deviation

S-Slope of calibration curve

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma$$

$$S \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 2}$$

Where,

σ - Standard deviation

S-Slope of calibration curve

Table 2.2: LOD and LOQ

LOD & LOQ			
Sr. No.	Parameter	Enalapril Maleate	Hydrochlorothiazide
1.	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.8908	0.5423
2.	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	2.6993	1.6432

CONCLUSION:

In present research work separation of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide was carried out in less than 8 min run time by using simple chromatographic conditions at ambient temperature using two component mobile phase (Methanol: Acetonitrile: Buffer pH 4.5 adjusted with OPA) in the ratio of 40: 30:30 at 230nm. System suitability parameters showed that the method is appropriate and found to be satisfactory the estimation of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide in tablet dosage form. The HPLC method was validated as per ICH guidelines for specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness, LOD and LOQ. All the validation parameters were found to be well within the acceptable limit. The assessment of robustness and ruggedness of the method indicates that the method remains unaffected by slight changes in chromatographic conditions. Hence, method can be used for the routine analysis of Enalapril Maleate and Hydrochlorothiazide in bulk and dosage form.

FUNDING: Nil

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION:

All author have contributed equally

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

All author have declared no conflict of interest.

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